
Impact of Unemployment on Crime Rate in Nigeria (1985-2022)

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the effect of unemployment on crime rate in Nigeria for the period 1990-2022. The dependent variable was crime rate while the independent variables were unemployment rate, labour force participation rate and higher education enrolment rate. The data were sourced from the World Bank publication 2022 edition. The data were subjected to econometric analysis of unit root, Johansen co-integration test and the error correction model estimation. The results revealed a positive and significant relationship between unemployment rate and crime rate in Nigeria. Labour force participation rate significantly decreased crime rate in Nigeria and higher education enrolment rate increased crime rate in Nigeria but the increase was not found to be significant. The study concluded that the continued increase in unemployment rate has not augured well for the economy because labour force participation rate is low which puts more pressure on the rate of unemployment thus increasing crime rate in the country. School enrolment has not significantly helped matters as crime rate has still not significantly reduced. It was therefore recommended that government need to embark on serious youth employment drive by way of capacity building, youth empowerment programmes, expenditure on job creation and as well government need to go into public-private partnership in a bid to increase labour force participation especially in the private sector so as to reduce idleness which increases crime rate.

KEYWORDS: Crime, Unemployment, Labour, Force, Rate

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INTRODUCTION

Unemployment is generally seen as the situation where people that are able and willing to work are unable to find a suitable work to sustain their livelihood. The nexus between unemployment and crime rate can be likened to a direct effect whereby increase in one, results to increase in the other, (Ajaegbu, (2022).

Historically, in the 1980s, stark economic inequality and deprivation, by social disorganization, and inadequate government service and law enforcement capabilities pushed crime rate to high proportions in Nigeria as reported by Ndifon, Apor, & Ndifon, (2022). Published crime statistics by the Nigeria Police in the 1980s were probably grossly understated, because most of the country was virtually unpoliced (NBS, 2020). Security was concentrated in urban areas where only about 25 percent of the population lived and public distrust of the police contributed to underreporting of crimes. Annual crime rates fluctuated at about 200 per 100,000 populations until the early 1960s and then steadily increased to more than 300 per 100,000 by the mid1970s (NBS, 2020).

Available data from the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS, 2020) indicated a continuing increase in crime rate from 1980s to the late 1990s. Total reported crimes rose from almost 211,000 in 1981 to between 330,000 and 355,000 during 1984-85 and surpassed one million in 1998.

The British High Commission in Lagos in 2010 cited more than 3,000 cases of forgeries annually. In years past 2010, the crime wave was exacerbated by worsening economic conditions and by the ineffectiveness, inefficiency, and corruption of police, military, and customs personnel who colluded and conspired with criminals or actually engaged in criminal conduct. Drug-related crime emerged as a resort to the rising unemployment situation in Nigeria at the time estimated at nearly 15% (NBS, 2020).

A popular adage says, an idle hand is a devil's workshop. This implies that only an inactive individual will imagine evil all of the time because he or she is not actively engaged. Unemployment is the one of the major causes of the rise in crime in Nigeria. Nigeria has a 21.14% unemployment rate in 2010. In 2011, it rose to 23.9%, and also by 2012, it had significantly risen to 27.4%. However, the unemployment rate decreased to 24.7% in Q4 2013 and increased up to 25.1% in Q4 2014. As at Q4 2015, this was 10.44%,

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14.23% by Q4 2016, 20.42% by Q4 2017, 23.13% by Q3 2018, and 33.30% by Q4 2020 according to the report from National Bureau of Statistics (NBS, 2020). Thus, Nigeria's unemployment rate was 27.10% as of the second quarter of 2020, and it increased to 33.30% by the fourth quarter that same year. Particularly, as of Q1-2021, unemployment was 30.7%. Unfortunately, Nigeria's unemployment rate is as high as 40% in recent times, since 2020.

Unemployment and crime rate are major social problems in Nigeria, and their negative impact on the country's economy and society are well documented. However, the causal relationship between these two terms is not well understood, and the factors that drive the association are not also clearly identified. This makes it difficult to design effective policies to address these issues. This statement highlights the need for a better understanding of the relationship between unemployment and crime, and the factors that influence them, in order to develop more effective policies to address the issue accordingly.

Unemployment and crime rate pose some time un-identified various problems in the society and the world at large, especially in underdeveloped and developing nations like Nigeria. In terms of unemployment, the high levels of joblessness contribute to poverty, inequality, and other social unrest. Thus, this can lead to a vicious cycle of deprivation and violence, and can however, undermine social cohesion and trust. In terms of crime, the high rate of violence and crime can disrupt economic activity and discourage possible investment, which in turn can further exacerbate unemployment. Therefore, the main objective of this study is generally to investigate the impact of unemployment on crime rate in Nigeria. While the specific objectives are to:

1. Examine the effect of unemployment rate on crime reduction in Nigeria.
2. Investigate the impact of labour force participation on the reduction of crime in Nigeria.
3. Determine the effect of higher education enrolment on the reduction of crime in Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptual Review

Crime

Ordinarily, crime can be said to be a threat to the economic, political and social security of a nation and a major factor associated with underdevelopment; as it discourages both local and foreign investments, reduces the quality of life, destroys human and social capital, damages relationship between citizens and the states, thus undermining democracy, rule of law, the ability of the country to promote development and such.

According to Oxford Dictionary of Sociology (2009), "a crime is held to be an offence, which goes beyond the personal and into public sphere, breaking prohibitory rules or laws, to which legitimate punishments or sanctions are attached and which requires the invention of a public authority for crime to be known as such, it must come to the notice of, and be processed through, an administrative system or enforcement agency. It must be reported and recorded by the police or other investigator; it may become part of criminal statistics; may or may not be investigated, may or may not result in a court case."

Dambazu (2019), defines crime as an act or omission against public interest and which is prescribed by law enacted by the legislature in the overall interest of the society, and to which prescribed punishments is attached to in the event of violation and it involves four major principles which are public wrong, moral wrong, law and punishment for the criminal. Crime is also seen as a violation of the rules agreed to be respected by all members of the society, and upon which the rest members of the society mete sanctions upon those guilty of the violation. It is for the same reason that the legal system views crime as a public and moral wrong.

The prevalence of crime in the world today is a cause for serious concern for all and sundry. It undermines the social fabric by eroding the sense of safe and security. Crime impacts on society in a variety of ways according to the nature and extent of crime committed. It constitutes a problem when its incidence is as rampant in the society as to constitute a threat to security of persons and property, as well as social order and solidarity (Omoge, 2019).

The development in societies with particular references to westernization has not helped matters; instead, it has been destructive to the social and cultural values of the society. Reasons for the increase in crime in Nigeria include urbanization which is spreading more widely and rapidly than improvement in the social and economic condition. Crime is a huge threat to public safety. It causes great personal suffering, vast damage, and place enormous burden on the urban social network. Globally, every five years, 60% of city inhabitants have been victims of one type of crime or another while over half of these crimes have involved personal crime (arson fraudulence, cheating, 419 syndrome, forgery, etc.). It has been noted that Nigerian cities are conducive areas for criminal activities because they provide the anonymity needed for criminal activities (Okafor, 2021).

Crime in Nigeria

Crime rate Nigeria has assumed a worrisome dimension. In the light of the worrisome crime situation, and the effectiveness of the crime control apparatuses, Nigeria can be deemed to have a crime problem. Nigeria is among the developing countries of the world that is experiencing a prevalence of rising waves, criminal intentions and varying degree of delinquencies. Nigeria has been on global crime map since 1980s (Dambazau, 2019). The nature of these crimes includes armed robbery, rape, murder, car theft, fraud, burglary, bribery and corruption, food and drug adulteration, gambling, smuggling, human trafficking, kidnapping, drug trafficking, money laundering, internet scam, advanced fee fraud (419), ritualism, and other illegal activities.

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Okafor (2021), revealed a "training school" for jobless youths as armed robbers at Ajegunle area of Lagos. The said training school according to that report includes planning strategies of co-operation, launching an attack and escaping with loots. Their ages range between eighteen and twenty-eight years. The 'training school' also conducts interview for the recruit, and it was also revealed that the training school is where bandits prepare programmes on which area to raid and plan how to operate different types of fire arms and ammunition. Suspects were nabbed during their morning training session where they were working out modalities on a number of houses to be raided for the week (Adebayo 2021).

Unemployment

The International Labour Organization (ILO, 2019), defines the unemployed as the number of the economically active population who is without work but available and seeking work, including people who have lost their jobs and those who have voluntarily left work (World Bank, 2019).

According to the National Bureau of statistics (NBS, 2020), the labour force of country is a set of people or citizens who are willing and are able to make available at any given point in time their efforts for gainful employment, while the employed are individuals with no work, but are looking for work at the time of any study.

The ILO (2019) report showed that the proportion of the world unemployment is steadily increasing and that the number of those without jobs remained at an all-time high of more than 195million or 6.3% in 2021. Record has it that the Middle east and North Africa were the regions had the highest unemployment rate in the world at 12.2%, followed by Sub-Saharan Africa at nearly 10%. East Asia's unemployment rate of 3.6% remained the lowest (ILO, 2019).

Unemployment as a global concern in recent times, because its dire consequence for youth's employment and the economy in general. Global youth's unemployment rate was projected at 12.7% in 2012. This portends immense dangers when understood from the point of view that young people are the next generation of potentially productive economic and social actors. In Africa, youth's unemployment has been a major problem giving rise to other criminal tendencies in youths and threatens the social-economic peace and stability of the continent (Ajufo, 2023).

Causes of Unemployment in Nigeria

Noticeably of late, the over emphasis on University certificates and neglect on skill acquisition, trainings have contributed to youth and general unemployment.

The level of unemployment is highly dependent on the overall status of the economy (Awogbenle & Iwuamadi, 2020). Despite its riches from oil economy, employment in Nigeria is actually falling. The years of corruption civil war, military rule, and mismanagement has hindered economic growth. Nigeria is endowed with diverse and infinite resources, both human and material but years of negligence and diverse policies have led to the under-utilization of these resources.

Nigeria has a total population of about 140million people as per 2006 census and this figure is projected to be over 200million by 2025 if the annual growth rate of 3.2% continues (National Population Commission and ICF Macro, 2019). While the population increases, the number of industries growth is dwindling and if nothing serious is done, both population and unemployment will continue to rise.

The outdated school curricula and lack of employable skills have also contributed to the level of unemployment in Nigeria. Some scholars have argued that as far as the formal sector is concerned, the average Nigerian graduate is not employable therefore, does not possess the skills needed by the employers (Anyadike, Emeh & Ukah, (2022).

Sanusi (2017), noted that the adopting of untimely economic policy measures contributed to the demise of small scale and cottage industries operated in both formal informal sectors. Thus, following the introduction of structural adjustment programs in September 1986 that ushered in liberalization, deregulation and devaluation program of the domestic currency, many of the teething domestic firms collapsed that resulted in serious job losses.

According to Alanana (2023), the total number of graduates produced in Nigeria was 73,339 in 1986/1987 that rose to 131,016 in 1996/1997 and now over one million as at 2022. Over a thousand universities occur in Nigeria with a demand for higher education while there is a problem of unemployment. The reality is that the economy does not have the capacity to absorb all unemployed graduates because over 800 industries and 100 factories were closed down in 2019 alone.

Nigeria's Unemployment and Crimes

Unemployment accounts for most of the social crimes perpetrated by youth in the Nigerian society today. The accelerating level of armed robbery, rape, murder, car theft, fraud, burglary, bribery and corruption, food and drug adulteration, gambling, smuggling, human trafficking, kidnapping, drug trafficking, money laundering, bunker, adoption, internet scam, advanced fee fraud (419), ritualism, and other illegal activities can largely be attributed to the incidence of unemployment..

Eze, (2021), noted that an examination of most of the apprehended criminals show that a large number of youth that engage in criminal activities are those without gainful employment. Some of them are those who have the potentials for gainful employment but have been denied such opportunity. She states emphatically that unemployment then can be seen as one of the core causes of the rising level of social disorder and insecurity permeating the entire country of Nigeria.

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A 2009 World Bank report on 'Employment and Growth' noted that, the share of young people between the ages of 15 and 24 outside the labour force is on the increase and the attendant laying off of workers in many sectors of the economy is fast driving crime rate to higher proportions (AllAfrica, 2020). The UN-Habitat study on crimes and violence stressed that socio-economic inequality and the lack of opportunities for social advancement and employment are some of the root causes of crimes and violence. Children and youth from disadvantaged families are vulnerable to fall prey to criminal networks. Thus, the estimated 1 billion people living in slums, over half are under the age 25, and 40% are estimated to be under the age of 19. They are the primary victims of social exclusion through unemployment, lack of access to health and education (UN-Habitat, 2018).

Furthermore, an empirical survey of Children and Youth in Organized Armed Violence in Nigeria by World Bank (2019), reported that disenchantment and frustration of young people due to mass poverty and unemployment, has increased the number of aggrieved youths and resulted in the emergence of area boys and Almajiris who target the very society that alienated them. The survey concluded that, armed militants groups in Nigeria namely Bakassi Boys, Oodua Peoples Congress (OPC) and Egbesu Boys were made of youths within 16-17 years (40%), 18-19 years (10%), 20-21 years (20%). Approximately 60% of the, were unemployed (Awogbenle & Iwuamadi, 2020).

Ademola and Olajubutu (2019), noted that the three tiers of government should effectively tackle unemployment in order to reduce crime rate in Nigeria. He expressed concern at the rate youths were resorting to crime as an alternative means of survival due to unemployment: "We have a lot of graduates and even those who have not attended any school who have nothing to do. It becomes worrisome, when you go around this country and you see the faces of unemployed persons. You begin to wonder that we just have to do what we have to do at the level of federal, state and local governments to begin to plan and put policies in place for the employment of these persons".

Ajufo (2023), maintained that desperation as a result of unemployment can drive many people into living outside the law in order to survive and as a means of expressing dissatisfaction for the apparent neglect of their very existence. She noted further that the negative consequences include poverty, psychological problems, and all manner of criminal behaviour causing general insecurity of life and businesses across the nation.

Okonkwo (2015), observed that crime in Nigeria may be a consequence of unemployment, but it is also an additional factor causing youth unemployment through its negative effects on the economy. He pointed out that crime affects the economy through a number of channels/ways.

Ideyi (2015), had noted, businesses which could not relocate to safer environment in the country and in the South-South and South-East geo-political zones in particular, closed-down out rightly and their contributions to national output sized while many were also thrown into the labour market again. It is a kind of vicious cycle in that the activities of those who are not employed will cause the very few that got paid employment to become the unemployed as well.

Tejumola (2020), has reported that the high level of insecurity in some parts of Nigeria also created a very bad perception in the international community with grave consequences for Nigerian businesses seeking partnership and other forms of deals with foreign firms.

According to him, in-country businesses were already bogged down by the poor state of electricity generation and supply, forcing many to shut-down, but the growing rate of kidnapping in parts of the country can only ruin businesses and chase investors away. As he opined, the level of insecurity in some parts of the country is killing businesses.

THEORETICAL LITERATURE REVIEW

Deprivation Theory of Ted Gurr (1970)

This classical theory explains why people engage in violence (riots, rebellion, coups, criminal activities etc.). It examines the psychological causes involving frustration and aggression as the primary source of human capacity for violence. Frustration is neither necessary nor sufficiently leads to violence but greed may drive to violence. Frustration is a much stronger motivating force and prolonged frustration may cause greater probability for aggression. Relative deprivation is the discrepancy between what people think they deserve and what they actually think they can get (Gurr, 1970).

It is noteworthy that Gurr does not look to a more absolute or objective indicator of deprivation as the source of violence. People can get used to a bad state of affairs, even one that offers so little access to life-sustaining resources that members of the group are starving or dying of remediable diseases or exposure. However, if there is a significant discrepancy between what they think they deserve and what they think they will get, there is a likelihood of rebellion. Gurr posits this to be the case because there is a feeling that their expectation cannot be met if the current status quo is maintained. The first situation may be a desperate one, but it is the second that will be frustrating. So frustration produces aggression at individual, group and societal levels.

This theory could be used to link rising number of unemployed youths and violent crimes in Nigeria. A country that produce thousands of university graduate every year without commensurate employment opportunities may be creating a fertile ground for a feeling of frustration among these unemployed graduates.

Classical Theory of Unemployment

Pigou (1933), McDonald and Solow (1981) examined the classical theory of unemployment and made a case that the labour market comprises of the demand for and supply of labour. Demand for labour is a derived demand, gotten from the falling off of the marginal product of labour. The demand curve is an inverse relationship of the real wage in the sense that if real wages increase, the quantity demanded for labour will fall and vice versa.

The supply of labour is gotten from employee's decision whether to spend part of their time working or not working. Supply of labour has a direct relationship with the real wage, because if the real wage increases, employees supply more labour hours. The classicalists opined that occasionally wages would decrease and there would be no unemployment except for frictional unemployment which is caused by time delay between leaving one job and starting another. This school of thought proposes that urban unemployment problem can be traced to the fault of employees and the numerous trade unions power. They believed strongly in market forces.

Empirical Literature Review

Adejumobi (2021), adopted chi square methodology to test the effect of crime rate in Nigerian economic growth, (1986-2009) and discovered that most people work to earn a living, to make money and to confer a sense of achievement. In other words, being employed makes one happy, wanted and needed in the society. The converse is unemployment. It is not only dehumanizes the affected individual directly, but also turns him or her into liability in the society.

Uddin (2023), used linear equation to analyzed the impact of youth unemployment on economic growth in Nigeria. The study concluded that conglomerate of youths with diverse background, willing and able to work, but cannot find any or cannot find the type of job that they are trained to do and which they will be proud of as their area of expertise. Such a situation has a pronounced socio-economic consequence which may weaken and damage the moral fabrics of the affected youths and societies.

Ogbebor, (2022), tested the consequences upon the intensity of youth unemployment in Nigeria, and concluded that some of the youths tend to lose their moral conscience in order to meet the basic necessities of life. These categories of youths often see themselves as forgotten generation and are psychologically dejected for being unable to contribute productively to the society. This situation has increasingly encouraged criminality among youths such as armed robbery, murder, assassination and arson.

Paranjape (2022), carried out a research on essential part of social behaviours and economic growth in developing nations in which emanates out of the relationship of individual in the society. The study concluded that a man or woman resorts to criminal act out of his or her intelligence and free will. The paradox of it is that no one is born a criminal, but it is the circumstance that makes him or her so, not because he or she wants to be a criminal, but rather forced to lend to criminality. Within this sort of context, youth-unemployment and criminality constitute an intertwined social problem which are mutually reinforcing. They are both symptoms of social disorganization in the society.

Ololo and Meisamari, (2022), adopted SPSS technique to access the effects of unemployment on the youths in Nigeria from a broad spectrum of socio-economic groups both the less educated and well-read. And concluded that, the rising wave of criminality, which has devastating effects on the society is traceable to various factors such as unemployment, poverty and greed among others.

Anderson (2019), adopted a scientific research using co-integration to test the relationship between crime and unemployment and observed that when the wider economy fails, many people particularly the youths go underground and take to crime. They seize such negative opportunity because they see it as an avenue to seek revenge on a system that has provided them nothing but frustration. Thus, most of those who engage in criminality in Nigeria are mostly young, educated persons who complain about hunger and unemployment.

Obaro (2022), used a scientific methodology to analyze the relationship between crimes and unemployment and further indicated that violent crimes committed in Nigerian societies of contemporary times involve the youth in most cases. For instance, an analysis of most of the apprehended criminals in the country shows that a large chunk of the young people that engage in criminal activities are those without gainful employment.

Figures supplied by the Nigerian Prisons Service to the National Bureau of Statistics (2020), indicated that in 2006, the number of people aged 16-35years, in convict prisons was 49.8% and in 2008, the number almost doubled, increasing astronomically to 92.5% within a period of 3 years. Ogbebor (2022), reaffirmed that over 70 percent of Nigerian prisoners these days are young people and majority of these persons are youths. Also available statistics from the Nigeria Police crime-records showed that, between the periods of 2005-2019; 16,925 robbery suspects were arrested by the police and majority of them were youths (Cleen Foundation Crime Report, 2020).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed ex-post-facto research design. The choice of this research design was considered appropriate because of its advantages of identifying relatable attributes of a set of data that has been collected and kept for records purposes by a known authority.

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Model Specification

The model is a simple equation represented as:

$$Y=F(X)$$

Where Y is the dependent variable which is crime rate, and X is the explanatory variable or independent variable which is unemployment. By relating it to our work, we have:

$$CR=F(UNR) \quad \dots(3.1)$$

Where:

CR=Crime rate %

UNR=Unemployment rate in %

We now expand the right hand side which is 'UNR' by introducing the variables that affect crime rate thus:

$$CR=f(UNR,LFP,HEE) \quad \dots(3.2)$$

Where:

CR and UNR are as previously defined

LFP = labour force participation

HEE = higher education enrolment

By representing the equation in a linear econometric expression, we have:

$$CR_t = a_0 + a_1UNR_t + a_2LFP_t + a_3HEE_t + c_{1t} \quad \dots(3.3)$$

Where:

ao = Intercept or the constant

$a_1 - a_3$ = Unknown coefficients of the model to be estimated

ϵ_H = Errorterm

The a-priori expectation is such that $UNR < 0, LFP < 0, HEE < 0$ and $HCD < 0$. That is to say that the coefficients of the explanatory variables should be negative or have decreasing effect on crime rate in Nigeria, in line with economic theories.

Test for Stationarity of the Data

Summary of the Unit Root Test

Variables	ADF test statistics		Order of Integration	Decision
	Level	1st Difference		
CR	-0.096780	-3.434098	I(1)	Stationary at 1st difference
UNR	-0.889357	-10.42006	I(1)	Stationary at 1st difference
LFP	-0.670041	-6.501345	I(1)	Stationary at 1st difference
HEE	-0.502353	-9.551225	I(1)	Stationary at 1st difference
Critical Values				
1% (*)	-3.621023	-3.621023		
5% (**)	-2.941145	-2.943427		
10% Source: Ext	-2.610263	-2.609066		

Co-integration Test

Johansen Co-integration Test Result

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Trace Statistic Result			Max-Eigen Statistic Result		
		Trace Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**	Max-Eigen Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
None*	0.5572	58.216	54.818	0.0242	37.701	33.876	0.0226
At most 1	0.3294	30.514	47.856	0.6923	13.590	27.584	0.8498
At most 2	0.2958	16.924	29.797	0.6456	11.928	21.131	0.5548
At most 3	0.0957	4.9966	15.494	0.8092	3.4219	14.264	0.9147

Error Correction Model Estimation

Summary of the ECM Estimates

Variable	Coefficient	Std.Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	23.21209	0.841579	27.58158	0.0000
UNR	0.419104	0.111406	3.761939	0.0014
LFP	-0.284591	0.057605	-4.940402	0.0001

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HEE	0.139246	0.098473	1.414048	0.1744
ECM(-1)	-0.066445	0.026520	-2.505468	0.0251
R-squared	0.936483	Durbin Watson st	at	31.12964
Adjusted R-squared	0.918840	F-statistic		53.07816

Researcher's Computation from Eviews 9

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One:

Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between unemployment rate and reduction in crime rate in Nigeria.

t-statistic = 3.7619 (p-value=0.0014)

t-table = 2.560

Hypothesis Two:

Ho₂: No significant relationship exists between labour force participation rate and reduction in crime rate in Nigeria.

t-statistic = -4.9404 (p-value = 0.0001)

t-table = 2.560

Hypothesis Three:

Ho₃: Higher education enrolment rate has no significant relationship and reduction in crime rate in Nigeria.

t-statistic = 1.414 (p-value=0.1744)

t-table = 2.560.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Unemployment variables have long run positive impact on crime rate in Nigeria.

Higher education enrolment has positive and direct relationship with crime rate in Nigeria.

Labour force participation rate exert a significantly negative effect on crime rate in Nigeria.

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

There is a positive and significant relationship between unemployment rate and crime rate in Nigeria. That is to say that unemployment rate increased crime rate significantly.

Labour force participation rate significantly decreased crime rate in Nigeria.

Higher education enrolment rate increased crime rate in Nigeria but the increase was not found to be significant.

CONCLUSION

Conclusively, unemployment rate is the leading cause of increased crime rate in Nigeria. The continued increase in unemployment rate has not augured well for the economy because labour force participation rate is low which puts more pressure on the rate of unemployment thus increasing crime rate in the country.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Government needs to embark on serious youth employment drive by way of capacity building, youth empowerment programmes, expenditure on job creation and such.

Labour force participation rate needs to be increased by human capital investment. Thus, government needs to go into public-private partnership in a bid to increase labour force participation especially in the private sector.

School enrolment can be further increased in Nigeria by enforcing a free and compulsory secondary school education with adequate penalized on defaulters in the country.

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